

Supplementary information

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#Equal contribution

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1 Scanning electron microscopy

Figure S1 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of: (A) PP 1 extract, (B) empty GPs, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 1 composites, (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 1 composites. Scale bars represent (A) 100 μm, (B, C, D) 10 μm.

Figure S2 Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of: (A) PP 2 extract, (B) empty GPs, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 2 composites, (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 2 composites. Scale bars represent (A) 100 μm, (B, C, D) 10 μm.

2 X-ray powder diffraction

Figure S3 X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns of: (A) pure GPs, (B) PP 1 extract, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 1 composites and (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 1 composites.

Figure S4 X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) patterns of: (A) pure GPs, (B) PP 2 extract, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 2 composites and (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 2 composites.

3 Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared spectra

Figure S5 Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectra of: (A) pure GPs, (B) PP 1 extract, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 1 composites and (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 1 composites.

Figure S6 Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform Infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectra of: (A) pure GPs, (B) PP 2 extract, (C) spray dried GPs/PP 2 composites, and (D) rotary evaporated GPs/PP 2 composites.

4 UV-VIS spectrophotometry

Figure S7 UV-VIS spectra of propolis extract (PP) and glucan particles (GPs).

5 Solubility of propolis extracts

Figure S8 Solubility of propolis extracts with the addition of various concentrations of surfactant SDS (1; 0.75; 0.5; 0.25; 0%) after 48 hours at 37°C; ; ■ PP1; ■ PP2, ■ PP3.

6 Composition of propolis extracts and composites

Figure S9 UHPLC-HRMS/MS fingerprints of methanolic extracts of propolis (blue) and composites (red) in positive (A) and negative (B) electrospray ionization mode, 1 – propolis 1 extract (PP 1) and composites (GPs/PP 1), 2 – propolis 2 extract (PP 2) and composites (GPs/PP 2), 3 – propolis 3 extract (PP 3) and composites (GPs/PP 3).

7 *In vitro* bioactivity

Cytotoxicity

Table S1 Concentration of propolis and glucan halving the viability (IC₅₀) of **primary human renal tubular epithelial cells (HRTEC)**.

Solution	Propolis (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)				Glucan (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)
	DMSO	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	276 ± 8 ^e	396 ± 27 ^f	>124	83 ± 1 ^b	-
PP 2	86 ± 1 ^b	139 ± 8 ^d	>220	93 ± 6 ^{b,c}	-
PP 3	69 ± 7 ^b	121 ± 1 ^{c,d}	>61	37 ± 4 ^a	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The effect of propolis administration was statistically evaluated using Compact Letter Display renders one-way ANOVA followed by Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Anti-inflammatory activity

Table S2 Concentration of propolis and glucan halving production of **NO** by LPS-stimulated macrophages (RAW 264.7).

Solution	Propolis (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)				Glucan (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)
	DMSO	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	33 ± 3 ^d	18 ± 1 ^b	38 ± 1 ^{d,e}	15 ± 1 ^b	-
PP 2	26 ± 1 ^c	20 ± 1 ^{b,c}	73 ± 4 ^g	20 ± 1 ^{b,c}	-
PP 3	53 ± 3 ^f	26 ± 1 ^c	39 ± 2 ^e	8 ± 1 ^a	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The resulting values of Propolis IC₅₀ were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Table S3 Concentration of propolis and glucan halving production of **TNFα** by LPS-stimulated macrophages (RAW 264.7).

Solution	Propolis (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)			Glucan (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)
	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	>396	>124	46 ± 4	-
PP 2	>139	>220	57 ± 1	-
PP 3	>121	>61	>37	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM.

Table S4 Concentration of propolis and glucan halving production of **IL-6** by LPS-stimulated macrophages (RAW 264.7).

Solution	Propolis (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)			Glucan (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)
	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	13.1 ± 1.2 ^d	37.5 ± 0.3 ^f	10.2 ± 0.1 ^c	-
PP 2	7.9 ± 0.3 ^b	58.4 ± 2.2 ^g	7.3 ± 0.2 ^b	-
PP 3	4.1 ± 0.1 ^a	24.2 ± 0.9 ^e	3.9 ± 0.1 ^a	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	166.1 ± 12.9

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The resulting values of Propolis IC₅₀ were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Antioxidant activity

Table S5 Concentration of propolis and glucan halving the **free radicals** in macrophages RAW 264.7 after addition of 2,2'-Azobis(2-amidinopropane) dihydrochloride (AAPH) in PBS.

Solution	Propolis (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)				Glucan (IC ₅₀ , mg/L)
	DMSO	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	>276	115 ± 8 ^c	>124	44 ± 1 ^{a,b}	-
PP 2	59 ± 5 ^b	59 ± 3 ^b	>220	>93	-
PP 3	38 ± 2 ^a	49 ± 4 ^{a,b}	>61	>37	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The resulting values of Propolis IC₅₀ were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Antimicrobial activity

Table S6 Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of propolis and glucan against *Candida albicans*.

Solution	Propolis (MIC, mg/L)				Glucan (MIC, mg/L)
	DMSO	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	549 ± 29 ^c	959 ± 79 ^d	>124	>172	-
PP 2	232 ± 7 ^b	270 ± 10 ^b	>220	58 ± 9 ^a	-
PP 3	251 ± 22 ^b	320 ± 7 ^b	>61	70 ± 7 ^a	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The resulting values of Propolis MIC were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Table S7 Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of propolis and glucan against *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Solution	Propolis (MIC, mg/L)				Glucan (MIC, mg/L)
	DMSO	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	679 ± 13 ^d	>1000	>124	>172	-
PP 2	136 ± 16 ^b	380 ± 55 ^c	>220	>197	-
PP 3	130 ± 2 ^b	270 ± 32 ^c	>61	11 ± 1 ^a	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The resulting values of Propolis MIC were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

Table S8 Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of propolis and glucan against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Solution	Propolis (MIC, mg/L)				Glucan (MIC, mg/L)
	DMSO	Ethanol	Medium	GPs/PP in medium	Empty GPs in medium
PP 1	>1000	>1000	>124	>172	-
PP 2	386 ± 27 ^b	128 ± 15 ^a	>220	>197	-
PP 3	156 ± 16 ^a	131 ± 3 ^a	>61	>172	-
Empty GPs	-	-	-	-	>2000

Values represent mean (n=3) ± SEM. The resulting values of Propolis extracts MIC were statistically processed using Compact Letter Display renders one-factor ANOVA and Duncan's *post hoc* test, $p \leq 0.05$.

8 Wound healing

Figure S10 Wound closure on untreated cells (control 1: DMEM w/o serum) at different time intervals (24, 48 and 72 hours). Scale bars represent 200 μm .

Figure S11 Wound healing ability of empty GPs (control 2: glucan particles) at different time intervals (24, 48 and 72 hours). Scale bars represent 200 μm .

Figure S12 Wound healing of propolis 1 extract dissolved in organic medium (“Ethanol”), cell culture medium (“DMEM”), and encapsulated in glucan particles (“GPs/PP 1”) and dissolved in cell culture medium (DMEM) at different time intervals (24, 48 and 72 hours). Scale bars represent 200 μm .

Figure S13 Wound healing of propolis 2 extract dissolved in organic medium (“Ethanol”), cell culture medium (“DMEM”), and encapsulated in glucan particles (“GPs/PP 2”) and dissolved in cell culture medium (DMEM) at different time intervals (24, 48 and 72 hours). Scale bars represent 200 μm .